

**ОПТИМІЗАЦІЯ НЕІНВАЗИВНОЇ ДІАГНОСТИКИ
КОРОНАВІРУСУ SARS-CoV-2 У ЛЕГЕНЕВОМУ ЕКСПІРАТІ, ЯК
ЗБУДНИКА ЗАПАЛЕННЯ РЕСПІРАТОРНОЇ СИСТЕМИ У ДІТЕЙ**

**USE OF EXHALED BREATH CONDENSATE (EBC) AS NON-
INVASIVE APPROACH FOR THE DIAGNOSIS OF CORONAVIRUS SARS-
CoV-2 AS CAUSE OF RESPIRATORY INFLAMMATION IN CHILDREN**

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Summary: This study focuses on diagnosing COVID-19 by detecting SARS-CoV-2 via polymerase-chain-reaction from exhaled breath condensate samples.

Introduction. COVID-19 is diagnosed by detection of viral RNA of SARS-CoV-2 by the reaction of reverse-transcriptase-polymerase-chain-reaction (RT-PCR) from nasopharyngeal and /or oropharyngeal swabs. To date, this is the best sampling approach for detecting coronavirus disease. However, despite negative COVID-19 tests, there were clinical cases that presented symptoms suggesting coronavirus disease. Therefore, it should be considered important to test other bodily fluids for the presence of the SARS-CoV-2 virus and aid in diagnosing patients with suspected COVID-19.

Material and methods: The study took place at Regional Municipal Non-Profit Facility "Chernivtsi Regional Children's Clinical Hospital» where 14 pediatric patients have been admitted to treat infectious disease. A cohort study included boys – 28,6% and rural residents – 57,1% with an average age of 11,4±0,89. Clinical diagnosis of COVID-19 was confirmed using the Protocol “Medical treatment guidance of coronavirus disease (COVID-19)” № 762 dd. 02.02.2020 with amendments. Laboratory testings, to confirm coronavirus infection, were performed by relevant regional laboratories accredited by the Ministry of Health of Ukraine. Other lab tests and instrumental examinations were performed at hospital facilities. Diagnostic testing was carried out based on clinical and epidemiological characteristics. Nasopharyngeal or naso- and oropharyngeal swabs and exhaled breath condensate (EBC) were used to detect SARS-CoV-2 antigens. EBC and nasopharyngeal swab RT-PCR was confirmed positive for

SARS-CoV-2. The patients were examined and recommended treatment in accordance with applicable national standards and protocols.

Result: 2 patients have been diagnosed with acute upper respiratory tract infection (14.3%), 9 patients have been diagnosed with acute bronchitis (64.3%), and 3 others have been diagnosed with viral pneumonia (21.4%). The average duration of onset of symptoms to hospital admission was $3,8 \pm 0,43$ days. Upon admission, 64.3% of the patients had been tested positive for SARS-CoV-2, where result of 14,3% was inconclusive and 21,4% tested negative. Nasopharyngeal swabs (NPS) taken on $6,4 \pm 0,69$ day, tested positive for SARS-CoV-2 in 35,7% cases, 42,9% showed negative and 21,4% of the result were inconclusive. At the same time, EBC was positive in 42,9% cases and 57,1% was negative. However, it is important to note that in patients with a negative NPS, EBC PCR was positive for SARS-CoV-2 in 66,7% cases, while positive NPS patients had positive EBC in 100% cases.

Discussion: The presented study suggests that exhaled breath condensate (EBC) can be tested through method of PCR to detect SARS-CoV-2 antigens. Such method gives the possibility to improve COVID-19 disease diagnosis in pediatric patients with respiratory system inflammation.

Conclusion: This study aims to confirm that exhaled breath PCR tests to detect SARS-CoV-2 allows to improve diagnostic possibilities by 66,7% when compared to standard COVID-19 testing.

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